

Tomb of Sunan Giri, Gresik (East Java)

also known as "Makam Sunan Giri, Gresik"

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Islamic Traditions, Southeast Asian Religions, Religious Place, shrines, Sufi, Tomb

Sunan Giri (1442-1506) also known as Joko Samudro, Raden Paku, Muhammad Ainul Yaqin, or Sunan Satmata founded the Islamic principality of Giri (also known as Giri Kedaton). A member of the Wali Songo (revered saints of Islam in Indonesia, particularly Java), Sunan Giri was the son of Maulana Ishak (brother of Maulana Malik Ibrahim or Sunan Gresik). Both Babad Tanah Jawi and Serat Walisana chronicles agree that Sunan Giri descended from the Raja of Blambangan, a vassal of the Majapahit Empire, from his maternal side. The first two rulers of Giri (Sunan Satmata and Sunan Dalem), defended their Islamic principality against depredations of the Majapahit army, according to Javanese chronicles. After the demise of the Majapahit Empire in 1527, Sunan Dalem of Giri succeeded in bringing the port of Gresik under his rule. Dutch contemporaries during the first quarter of the seventeenth century referred to the Sunans of Giri as the " Moorish Popes" (Pigeaud and Graaf 1976). Under Sunan Giri's grandson, Sunan Prapen's leadership, the Court of Giri became the epicenter for the propagation of Islam to the Outer Islands of the Indies archipelago, particularly Lombok, Celebes, Borneo, and the Moluccas. Local inhabitants from the Outer Islands of Indonesia revere Sunan Giri as "Raja Bukit" (Pigeaud and Graaf 1976). Trained by Sunan Ampel in Ilmu Tasawuf (Sufi mysticism), Sunan Giri became the leader of the Wali Songo in 1478 subsequent to the demise of his mentor and assumed the title of Prabu Satmata (one of the names of Lord Siva in the Javanese language). A salient feature of Sunan Giri's dakwah (invitations for people to more fully embrace Islam) was the adjustment of Javanese cultural elements to Islam. For instance, Sunan Giri redesigned the Javanese wayang (shadow) puppets such that they did not contravene the Islamic proscription of representing the human form. Likewise, the architectural elements of the Sunan Giri tomb complex appropriate Javanese architectural elements such that they conform to Islamic principles.

Date Range: 1506 CE - 2020 CE

Region: Gresik, East Java

Region tags: Southeast Asia, Indonesia, East Java

The tomb of Sunan Giri is located on a hillock in Sidomukti Village, Gresik regency (East Java), 2.9 km from the city of Gresik. The shaded area of this map depicts the location of the Tomb of Sunan Giri and the jurisdiction of Gresik regency.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: K van Dijk and P. Nas, "Dakwah and Indigenous Culture: The Dissemination of Islam," *Bijdragen tot de Taal-, Land-en Volkenkunde* 154, no. 2 (1998): 218-35.

– Source 1: A. Cabaton, *Raden Paku, Sunan de Giri: Legende Musulmaine Javanaise* (Paris: Ernest Leroux, 1906).

Notes: The publication outlines the early life of Sunan Giri and the establishment of the Giri Pesantren (Islamic boarding school in Java).

– Source 1: Ricklefs, M. C. *A History of Modern Indonesia*. Stanford: Stanford University Press, 2001.

– Source 1: M.C. Ricklefs, *A History of Modern Indonesia since 1200* (Stanford: Stanford University Press, 2001).

– Source 2: J.L.A. Brandes, *Babad Tjerbon: Uitvoerige inhoudsopgave en noten* (Bataviaasch Genootschap van Kunsten en Wetenschappen and M. Nijhoff: Batavia and the Hague, 1911).

Notes: The early life of Raden Pakoe (known as Sunan Giri since the assumption of overlordship of Giri and Ampel subsequent to the demise of his mentor Sunan Ampel) is of immense interest to scholars specializing in the history of Islam on Java. The story of the origins of Sunan Giri is of interest. According to *Sejarah Banten*, a foreign holy man named Molana Usalam comes to Balambangan in the Eastern Salient (Oosthoek) of Java, an area where Islam was not in fact established until the late eighteenth century. The ruler of Balambangan has a daughter who is ill, but she recovers when Molana Usalam gives her betel-nut to chew. She is then given in marriage to Molana Usalam, but when he also asks the ruler of Blambangan to adopt Islam the latter refuses. Molana Usalam therefore departs from Balambangan, leaving behind the princess who is already pregnant. When she bears a son, he is thrown into the sea in a chest, as in the story of Moses (which is found in sura XX of the Qur'an as well as in the Bible). The chest is fished out of the sea at Gresik, where the boy is raised as a Muslim and later becomes the first Sunan of Giri. In contrast to *Sejarah Banten*, *Babad Tjirebon*, version J.L.A. Brandes (translated into Dutch) mentions that Djuraadilkubra married the princess of Blambangan. Djuraadilkubra tried to convert his father-in-law, the Raja of Blambangan to Islam but failed and the latter expelled the former. The son of Djuraadilkubra and the Blambangan princess was thrown into the sea, only to be rescued by Nji Gëde Pinatijan who named the child Bagus Samudra as he was rescued from the sea. The child was mentored by Raden Rahmat (Sunan Ampel) and was sent on a pilgrimage to Mecca along with the son of Sunan Ampel would later become famous as Sunan Bonang. Subsequent to their return, Bagus Samudra acquired the appellation of Ratu Pandita or the Spiritual Leader. Extant Javanese and Malay historical traditions pose questions related to credibility of primary sources (a methodological dilemma) for the historian specializing on the early history of Islam in Java. Nevertheless, despite the uncertainty shrouding dates, events or lineages of the Wali Songo saints, the historical traditions reflect how successive Javanese remembered the Islamization of Java.

– Source 1: Sunyoto, Agus. *Atlas Wali Songo : Buku Pertama Yang Mengungkap Wali Songo Sebagai Fakta Sejarah*. Pustaka IIMaN and Lesbumi PBNU, 2017.

– Source 1: Ricci, Ronit. "Conversion to Islam on Java and the Book of One Thousand Questions." *Bijdragen Tot de Taal-, Land-En Volkenkunde* 165, no. 1 (February 25, 2009).
<https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1163/22134379-90003641>.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.loc.gov/item/2012320671/>

– Source 1 Description: *Pangkat-Pangkat Caritanipun Serat Babad ing Tanah Jawi Sedhaya: Awit Gusti Nabi Adam dumugi sapunika* (1862)

Notes: *Babad Tanah Jawi* (Javanese language in the Pegon script, 1862) sourced online from the Library

of Congress Manuscript and Mixed Collection. Javanese illuminated manuscript on the history of Java and the spread of Islam by saints and rulers. Babad Tanah Jawi is a generic title for several chronicles written in the Javanese language. Details of historical events and accounts vary from one Babad to another, given that these were composed subsequent to the occurrence of the historical event. Yet, the Babad Tanah Jawi chronicles are an invaluable resource for historians specializing on the Islamization of the Indonesian archipelago. The chronicles collectively attribute the spread of Islam in Java to the Wali Songo (nine saints) although the name and relationships amongst these saints vary throughout the texts. Most Babad Tanah Jawi texts list nine saints though a few list ten. For historians specializing on the History of Islam in the Indies archipelago, the texts pose methodological questions related to source credibility and interpolation.

– Source 1 URL: <https://lib.ui.ac.id/detail.jsp?id=20187826>

Notes: Serat Wali Sana Call No: Cl.17-KS 80; Second Floor, Perpustakaan Universitas Indonesia Library
The Serat Walisana chronicle highlights the genealogy of the Wali Songo.

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– No

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

Type of elevation

– Hill

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Type of feature

– Terracing

– Other [specify]: The tomb complex of Sunan Giri is terraced (4 levels) whilst the tombs of Sunan Giri and his wife are located on the fourth level.

Reference: Anom, I. G. N., Sri Sugiyanti, and Hadniwati Hasibuan. Hasil Pemugaran Dan Temuan Benda Cagar Budaya PJP I. Direktorat Jenderal Kebudayaan, 1996.

https://www.google.co.in/books/edition/Hasil_Pemugaran_dan_Temuan_Benda_Cagar_B/BjXkCgAAQBAhl=en&gbpv=1

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

↳ Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– Yes

↳ Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Notes: Semi-urban area. Desa Sidomukti (Sidomukti Village) is situated within the jurisdiction of kecamatan (sub-district) Kebomas, kabupaten (district) Gresik. Gresik falls within Surabaya metropolitan area. The tomb is situated within a distance of two miles from Alun-Alun Gresik (Gresik town square). Refer to the map provided.

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– No

↳ One single feature

– Other [specify]: Multiple structures.

Notes: Includes the tomb of Sunan Giri and his family, and the Masjid Ainul Yaqin Sunan Giri.

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

↳ A group of features:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

Notes: The arrangement of Sunan Giri Tomb can be divided into three parts, namely profane, transition, and sacred areas. The profane area is settled at the very front (parking lot, several stairs leading to the tomb used for souvenir and food stalls). Then, the transition area includes tombs of the students and their families. At the very back area (tomb of Sunan Giri and mosque) is a sacred space, with the highest sanctity value.

Reference: Faidah, Mutimmatul. "Pilgrims' Spiritual Practices at the Tomb of Sunan Giri During the Covid Pandemic". *Advances in Social Science, Education and Humanities Research*, Volume 618 International Joint Conference on Arts and Humanities 2021 (IJCAH 2021) 618 (January 1, 2021). p.1010-14

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

– Healing

– Political

– Social

– Memorial

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

↳ In antiquity

– Once

↳ In modernity

– Post-Renaissance

Notes: The tomb was last renovated in 2012.

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Prayers are offered to Allah at the tomb of Sunan Giri. The saint is known to intercede on behalf of the devotees.

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Notes: Proscribed by Islam. In Islam, grave visitation (Javanese: ziarah) is highly contested. Whereas the Sufis regard ziarah as tawassul (a means that can be used to gain nearness to Allah), Wahhabis regard tawassul as akin to idolatry.

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Notes: Pious Javanese undertake ziarah (pilgrimage to the tomb of Sunan Giri) to commemorate the 40th day following the death of their family member and offer prayers. Veneration is the appropriate word here.

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

↳ Specify

- Religious specialists affiliated with political entity
- Other [specify]: The tomb of Sunan Giri was built in 1506. It was subsequently renovated by his grandson Sunan Prapen, who was the ruler of Giri between 1548 and 1605, according to Babad Tanah Jawi.

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

- Field doesn't know

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

- Yes

Specify

- Revelation occurred through divination

Notes: Sunan Giri, using his mystic powers is believed to have moved the grave of his mother Dewi Sekardadu from Banyuwangi, now in East Java province to Gresik. See the weblink below: <https://disparbud.gresikkab.go.id/2020/04/02/makam-dewi-sekardadu/>

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

- No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

- Yes

Specify

- War/battle

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

- I don't know

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

- Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

- No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– No

↳ Sand

– No

↳ Clay

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Plaster

– No

↳ Wood

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Grass

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

Notes: Limestone and black volcanic stone sourced locally. The gapura is built of limestone whilst the headstone of Sunan Giri is built of black volcanic stone, sourced locally and was used extensively in the construction of candis (Javanese shrines).

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Foundation of the tomb of Sunan Giri

Notes: Excerpted from Nur Wa'siah (2022): The tomb architecture is an exemplar of the fine blending between Hindu-Buddhist Javanese and Islamic elements. The split entrance gate (Javanese: gapura pintu) is sculpted of limestone and bears the carving of a naga head (dragon), reminiscent of an ancient candi. The foundation was built of red bricks whilst red jaggery was used as a mortar to bind the bricks together. The tomb of Sunan Giri is sheltered by a cupola. The cupola is built entirely of Javanese teakwood.

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: Cement used in the renovation of the foundation.

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

↳ On the inside:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– No

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Stylized Nagas (mythical dragon-snake influenced by Hindu mythology on Java) placed at the split gate leading to the shrine. See the black and white photo provided with the entry.

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– No

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

– Yes

Notes: On the walls of the tomb, geometric designs are evident. Several decorations, enclosed within a square field filled with hexagons and quadrilaterals, apparent.

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

Notes: Floral motifs and trellises on the wooden walls enclosing Sunan Giri's tomb.

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

Notes: In the Javanese language, using the Pegon script.

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Eclectic tomb architecture that incorporates Islamic and Javanese elements.

Notes: The entrance gate to the tomb (Gapura) is carved out of stone and features a pair of dragon heads (Nagaraja in Javanese mythology). The representation of living beings is proscribed in Islam. The wooden walls of the tomb contain panels that feature trellises (a conspicuous Islamic influence) whilst the door to the tomb features carvings that feature Hindu motifs. The roof of the tomb is a wooden three-tiered structure and is built in the Joglo or Javanese roof style. The apex of the tomb roof is marked by a mustaka (an ornamental feature resembling a crown).

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– Yes

↳ Can the decoration be revealed:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The Pegon calligraphy in Masjid Ainul Yaqin Sunan Giri is occluded from the pilgrim's view.

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– No

↳ Are there paintings present:

– No

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– Yes

Notes: Calligraphy in the Javanese language, using the Pegon script. The pegon script is derived from Arabic and was used to write commentaries on the al-Quran and Islamic poetry, particularly during the 15th and 16th centuries.

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative

[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

Notes: Sunan Giri's tombstone is sculpted from black stone, commonly used in the construction of pre-Islamic Javanese temples. The tombstone of Sunan Giri is covered with black cloth and bears an Arabic inscription that indicates the date of the saint's birth and death.

– Yes

Notes: A candra sengkala (chronogram) containing a Javanese inscription at the entrance gate. The chronogram declares that the entrance gate was built in 1506 (see Nur Was'ia 2022).

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Inscription in Pegon script. Descriptive.

↳ Other type of decoration:

– Yes [specify]: Trellis and floral motifs on the wall of the tombs of Sunan Giri's sons.

Notes: Unlike the wooden walls of Sunan Giri's tomb, the tomb walls of Sunan Giri's sons are built of stone and feature trellises and floral motifs. The tombstones reflect Javanese and Islamic influences.

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: Stylized naga sculpture gracing the split entrance gate leading to the shrine. For details see Nur Wasi'ah (2022).

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– Yes

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– Yes

Notes: The arrangement of the cupola is inspired by Hinduism and reflects the notion of bhurloka (realm of humans); bhuwarloka (realm of death); and, swarloka (heavens). But the original Hindu meaning is transformed in the Islamic context of monotheism. The cupola of the tomb is supported by four pillars (soko guru), an evidence of Javanese architecture. Each pillar represents a tenet of Islam: (a) syariah (Islamic religious law); (b) tarekat (a school or order of Sufism that seeks to discover the ultimate truth under the direction of a murshid or spiritual leader); (c) hakekat (essence); and, (d) ma'rifat (belief in One God).

Reference: Pradana, Rizal Wahyu Bagas. "Kajian Ikonografi Arsitektur Cungkup Makam Sunan

Giri". Jurusan Seni Rupa Dan Jurusan Desain Universitas Negeri Surabaya, September 19, 2019.
<https://media.neliti.com/media/publications/289424-kajian-ikonografi-arsitektur-cungkup-mak-c021dfff.pdf>.

↳ Humans

– No

Notes: Proscribed in Islam to represent living beings.

↳ Supernatural narratives

– No

↳ Human narratives

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: The entrance to Masjid Ainul Yaqin Sunan Giri also features a stylized Gapura Paduraksha (Javanese gate).

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– Yes

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Notes: People undertake ziarah (pilgrimage) to the shrine of Sunan Gresik to pray for their departed relatives.

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– Yes

↳ Human:

– No

↳ Animal:

– Yes

↳ How many animals are present:

– Number of animals: Field does not know.

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb/crypt:

– Yes

Notes: Apart from the tomb of Sunan Giri, the mausoleum includes the graves of Sunan Giri's wife and descendants (see Nur Wasi'ah 2022).

↳ Domestic context:

Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: N/A

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– No

↳ Are they sky deity:

– No

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– No

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– Yes

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

Notes: Sunan Giri assumed the appellation of Satmata Giri, a name of Lord Siva of the Hindu pantheon.

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Are they other:

– Other [specify]: Field does not know.

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– No

↳ In dreams:

– I don't know

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

Reference: Midaada, Arivista. "Ramalan Sunan Giri Dan Penaklukkan Mataram Atas Kesultanan Pajang Artikel Ini Telah Diterbitkan Di Halaman Sindonews.com Pada Selasa, 16 November 2021 - 10:02 WIB Oleh Avirista Midaada Dengan Judul "ramalan Sunan Giri Dan Penaklukkan Mataram Atas Kesultanan Pajang".". Sindo News, n.d..
<https://daerah.sindonews.com/read/600685/704/ramalan-sunan-giri-dan-penaklukkan-mataram-atas-kesultanan-pajang-1637028692>.

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

Notes: Sunan Giri and his descendants are believed to intercede on behalf of the pilgrims.

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Prayers to Allah. The saint is believed to intercede on the behalf of pilgrims. The juru kunci (key keeper) of the shrine apprises pilgrims regarding the rituals.

Are previously human spirits present:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– No

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: The saint is believed to intercede on the behalf of pilgrims. The juru kunci (key keeper) of the shrine apprises pilgrims regarding the rituals.

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural monitoring of norm adherence:

– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect offerings:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect proper ritual observance:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect performance of rituals:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect maintenance of the place:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect personal hygiene:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about honoring oaths:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Pilgrims plead for a favor (known in Javanese as *ngalap berkah*) and make a pledge to Allah (known as *nadhar*).
- ↳ Other:
 - Other [specify]: A culture of gifts and favours dominates at the shrines of Wali Songo. Gifts or offerings are made to the saint, verses from the Al-Quran are recited and pilgrims pray for favours known as *ngalap berkah* in Javanese.
 - Reference: Quinn, George. *Bandit Saints of Java: How Java's Eccentric Saints Are Challenging Fundamentalist Islam in Modern Indonesia*. Burrough on the Hill, Leicester: Monsoon Books, 2019.

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– No

Ritual and Performance

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

↳ Are there animal sacrifices:

– Yes [specify]: Ayam (chicken) is sacrificed on the 25th night of the Holy Month of Ramadhan in commemoration of Sunan Giri's son Sunan Dalem's recovery from illness.

↳ Are there human sacrifices:

– No

↳ Are the sacrificed humans associated in some way:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

– No

Notes: Customary.

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– No

Notes: Small denominations of cash and special meals to give thanks hosted by people who seek special favors from the saint.

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Prior to local elections in the province of East Java, candidates undertake a pilgrimage to the tomb of Sunan Giri to seek the saint's blessings at midnight.

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Notes: Customary is the correct word. It is customary to undertake ziarah to the shrines of Wali Songo during the holy month of Ramadan, offer special prayers for the deceased, or to seek a favor from the saint.

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

Notes: The most recent renovation of the shrine was undertaken in 1993.

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Secretariat of the shrine appoints staff in-charge of maintenance. The Juru Kunci is the caretaker of the tomb of Sunan Giri.

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: None

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

–optional (common)

Notes: Ziarah to the tomb of Sunan Giri and other shrines dedicated to the Wali Songo such as Sunan Ampel are customary. The ziarah coincide with important life events such as offering prayers for the deceased souls of relatives, seeking the saint's favor, or during the holy

month of Ramadhan.

↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:

– No

↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:

– Yes

↳ Birth

– Yes

↳ Transition to adulthood

– No

↳ Death

– Yes

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Candidates contesting in the local elections undertake ziarah to seek the saint's favors.

Notes: At the tomb area, pilgrims perform dhikr for the purpose of glorifying Allah and seeking spiritual refinement. Dhikr is a Sufi tradition. Tahlil prayers are offered for the soul of the deceased individual.

↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):

– Yes

↳ Are these routes maintained together with the place:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Yes

↳ Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

Notes: The Kolak Ayam tradition, when chicken of the ayam jago variety seasoned with spices, is served to devotees on the 25th night of Ramadhan, soon after the pilgrims break the fast on sighting the moon. The feasting commemorates the recovery of Sunan Dalem, Sunan Giri's son from illness.

↳ Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that built/maintains the place:

– Yes

↳ Priests

– No

↳ Local elites

– Yes

↳ Private contributions

– Yes

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Not known.

↳ Does feasting occur in a specific location within the place:

– Yes [specify]: At the shrine entrance.

Are festivals present:

– Yes

↳ Frequency of festivals

– specify: Annually. Festivals namely Malam Selawe, Kolak Ayam, Rebo Wekasan, Damar Kurung, Kirab Budaya Giri Kedaton.

Notes: Malam Selawe is the 25th night of the Holy Month of Ramadhan. On the night of Malam Selawe, pilgrims perform Dhikr (Sufi meditation in which prayers are repeatedly chanted), at the tomb of Sunan Giri, offer Tahlil prayers for the deceased, and recite Surat Yasin from the Al-Quran. Istighfar prayers are also offered at the tomb to seek forgiveness from Allah. Kolak Ayam is a feast that commemorates the convalescence of Sunan Dalem, Sunan Giri's son. The Ayam Jago variety of chicken that represents royalty is cooked for the feast that coincides with Malam Selawe. The feast marks the end of the 25th day of fasting during the Holy Month of Ramadhan. Rebo Wekasan is observed during the last Wednesday of the Islamic month of Safar to ward off natural disasters and diseases. The ritual continues since the 16th century. Rituals associated with the festival are observed in the village, situated about 5 miles from the tomb of Sunan Giri. The name of the Suci village originated from Sunan Giri's relative Syekh Jamaluddin Malik's discovery of an uncontaminated water source within the village's environs. Suci in bahasa Indonesia indicates purity/ sacredness. Rituals include Tolak Bala (that incorporates elements of local customs or adat and Islam). The rituals are intended to protect the community from natural disasters and symbolize the human soul's relationship with inhabitants of the unseen world. Select verses from the Al-Quran are recited. A feast consisting of tumpeng (Indonesian cone-shaped rice with serving of meat or vegetable) is served to the community. Damar Kurung is a bamboo- frame lantern, an artifact that is unique to Gresik. The artifact dates to pre-Islamic times and was influenced by the Chinese who have frequented the Pasisir (north coast of Java). Children traditionally lit Damar

Kurung Lanterns to welcome the Holy Month of Ramadhan. Kirab Budaya Giri Kedaton is the Gresik cultural festival.

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):

– All members

↳ Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:

– No

↳ On average, how many participants gather at this place:

– number: 80,000

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):

– Yes

↳ Is food consumption limited to certain members of the population:

– Elites

– Non-elites

– Religious professionals

– No

Notes: Kolak Ayam feast is traditionally prepared by men.

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– Yes

↳ Divination by examination of the exta:

Animals remains, internal organs, answer this question and subsequent question once for each species

– No

↳ Divination through human communication:

– Yes

↳ Is a human being the vehicle for the oracle:

– Yes

- ↳ Is a human being the interpreter of the oracle:
 - Yes
- ↳ Are the oracle interpreters of a specified sex/gender:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are the oracle interpreters of a specified ethnicity:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are the oracle interpreters of a specified class:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Is sex-deprivation required:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are intoxicants required:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Physical ordeal required:
 - Field doesn't know

↳ Divination through animal-behavior:

- Field doesn't know

↳ Divination through non-living material:

- Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Unknown.

↳ Other

- Other [specify]: Unknown.

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– Yes

↳ Incubation

- No

↳ Healing magic

– Yes

↳ Cleansing

– No

↳ Offerings of models of body parts:

– No

↳ Expiation

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Legend surrounding two noni trees planted outside the tomb of Sunan Giri

Notes: There is a little known legend related to the two perennially-fruiting ancient noni trees outside the tomb of Sunan Giri that bear a seedless variety of the fruit. According to Gresik locals, Sunan Giri recommended that students from his pesantren (Islamic boarding school in Java) end their Ramadan fast for the day by consuming these fruits.

Reference: Susanti, Duwi, Mujiman Andianto, and Furoidhatul Husniah. "Mitos Asal Usul Buah Biji Di Lingkungan Makam Sunan Giri". Artikel Hasil Penelitian Mahasiswa [Results of Student Research], December 10, 2013.

<https://repository.unej.ac.id/bitstream/handle/123456789/61742/Duwi%20Susanti.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>.

– Other [specify]: Used for infertility treatment.

Notes: Locals believe that consumption of the seedless noni fruits, available within the complex of Sunan Giri's tomb will enable infertile couples conceive and consider the fruit to be a barokah (blessing) of Allah.

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: On Malam Selawe and Rebo Wekasan. Collective reading of select verses of the Al-Quran, performance of Dhikr and the serving of the Kolak Ayam feast on Malam Selawe at the tomb of Sunan Giri . The ceremonial replacement of the draped cloth over Sunan Giri's tombstone is an annual feature at the shrine. The rituals commemorate the death anniversary of the saint and take place during the Islamic month of Robiul Awwal (the Islamic month of Mawlid). Reading of select verses from the al-Quran, followed by group recitation of surah tahlil verses, and performance of the Hadrah (a performing art native to eastern Java). After the recitation of Tahlil Akbar, nasi kebuli (Kabuli rice) is distributed to pilgrims as barokah (blessing)

of the saint. For details see Nurul Wasi'ah (2022).

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: Prayers offered for deceased relatives at the tomb of Sunan Giri.

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: 80,000 on Malam Selawe.

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: Yearly.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– Yes

Notes: Majelis Ulema Indonesia (The Indonesia Ulema Council) conducts orthodoxy checks.

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– Yes

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Yes

Notes: As observed during Malam Selawe

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– Yes

Notes: Juru Kunci or the caretaker of the tomb.

↳ Present part time
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:
– Yes
Notes: Javanese.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:
– Yes
Notes: Descendants of Sunan Giri

Reference: al-Ayyubi, Sudasir. "Kaum Giri Minta Bantuan Dewan Lurusan Tumpang Tindih Tupoksi Yayasan Makam Sunan Giri". *Javasatu.com*, n.d.. <https://jvasatu.com/culture/kaum-giri-minta-bantuan-dewan-luruskan-tumpang-tindih-tupoksi-yayasan-makam-sunan-giri/>.

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:
– Yes
Reference: Susanto, Bruriy. "Peristiwa Makam Sunan Giri, Puti Napak Tilas Kakeknya". *Merdeka.com*, n.d.. <https://www.merdeka.com/peristiwa/ziarah-makam-sunan-giri-puti-napak-tilas-kakeknya.html>.

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:
– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:
– Yes

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:
– Yes
Notes: See for e.g. Cabaton (1906).

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:
Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders
– Yes

Notes: Under Indonesia's decentralized administrative set-up, the management of the shrine is designated to the Gresik government. The Sunan Giri shrine has its own management committee that is responsible for management of the shrine.

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Yes

↳ Is a bureaucracy present permanently:

– Yes

Notes: The secretariat of the Sunan Giri shrine.

↳ Is a bureaucracy present on a temporary or seasonal basis:

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Field doesn't know

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Yes

↳ Public food distribution and/or storage:

– Yes

Notes: Food is served to the public on festivities such as Malam Seuwae.

– Yes

↳ Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):

– Yes

Notes: Cultural festival.

↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):

– No

↳ Function for water management:

– No

↳ Part of the transportation network:

– No

Other

– Other [specify]: Not known.

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The shrine of Sunan Giri contains a museum that has stored cultural artifacts having a religious significance such as the Keris Kalam Munyeng (an asymmetrical Javanese dagger that has spiritual significance used by Sunan Giri against the Majapahit army). Historical traditions such as Serat Centini note that when the Majapahit governor attacked Giri, there was commotion. At the time, Sunan Giri was copying verses from the Al-Quran with his pen. Suddenly, he threw the pen into the air and prayed to the Almighty. Miraculously, the pen of Sunan Giri was transformed into an heirloom keris that inflicted heavy casualties on the Majapahit troops.

Reference: Kemper, Simon. "The White Heron Called by the Muezzin: Shrines, Sufis and Warlords in Early Modern Java". In *Challenging Cosmopolitanism: Coercion, Mobility and Displacement in*, edited by Joshua Gedacht and Michael Feener. Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press, n.d..

https://www.google.co.in/books/edition/Challenging_Cosmopolitanism/C8hODwAAQBAJ?hl=en&gbpv=1&dq=joshua+gedacht+and+michael+feener&printsec=frontcover.

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Tomb of Sunan Giri, Gresik (East Java), Cabaton, A.. Raden Paku, Sunan De Giri: Legende Musulmain Javanaise. Paris: Ernest Leroux, n.d..

https://www.google.co.in/books/edition/Raden_Paku_Sunan_de_Giri/TENBAQAAMAAJ?hl=en&gbpv=1&dq=raden+paku+sunan+de+giri&pg=PA9&printsec=frontcover.

Reference: Tomb of Sunan Giri, Gresik (East Java), Wibowo, M. Sultan Haryo. Arsitektural Masjid Jami Gresik: Analisis Bentuk Simbol Dan Makna. UIN Sunan Ampel Surabaya, 2019.

Reference: Tomb of Sunan Giri, Gresik (East Java), Wasi'a, Nur. Simbol Simbol Pada Makam Sunan Giri. UIN Sunan Ampel Surabaya, 2022.

Reference: Tomb of Sunan Giri, Gresik (East Java), Mustakim, M.. Konstruksi Pemimpin Atas Tradisi Giri Sebagai Identitas Sosial Masyarakat Kabupaten Gresik. Malang: Universitas Muhammadiyah Malang (PhD Thesis), 2020. <https://eprints.umm.ac.id/65933/1/PENDAHULUAN.pdf>.

Reference: Tomb of Sunan Giri, Gresik (East Java), Izzatusshobikhah, Nurul. Penaklukan Mataram Terhadap Giri Kedaton, Tahun 1636-80. UIN Sunan Ampel Surabaya, n.d..

Reference: Tomb of Sunan Giri, Gresik (East Java), van Dijk, Kees, and P. Nas. "Dakwah and Indigenous Culture: The Dissemination of Islam". *Bijdragen Tot De Taal-, Land-en Volkenkunde* 154, no. 1 (July 6, 1998). <https://www.jstor.org/stable/27865428>. p.218-35

Reference: Tomb of Sunan Giri, Gresik (East Java), Ricci, Ronit. "Conversion to Islam on Java and the Book of One Thousand Questions". *Bijdragen Tot De Taal-, Land-en Volkenkunde* 165, no. 1 (February 25, 2009). <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1163/22134379-90003641>. p.8-31

Reference: Tomb of Sunan Giri, Gresik (East Java), Ricklefs, M. C.. *A History of Modern Indonesia*. Stanford: Stanford University Press, 2001.

Reference: Tomb of Sunan Giri, Gresik (East Java), Pigeaud, Theodore, and H. J. de Graaf. *Islamic States in Java, 1500-1700: A Summary*. Hague: Martinus Nijhoff, 1976.
https://www.google.co.in/books/edition/_/SgNXxQEACAAJ?hl=en&sa=X&ved=2ahUKEwiuyvO8hfv6AhXmTWwGHfxUBxMQre8FegQIDxAJ.

Reference: Tomb of Sunan Giri, Gresik (East Java), Sunyoto, Agus. *Atlas Wali Songo : Buku Pertama Yang Mengungkap Wali Songo Sebagai Fakta Sejarah*. Pustaka IIMaN and Lesbumi PBNU, 2017.

Entry/Answer References

Reference: Other [specify]: A culture of gifts and favours dominates at the shrines of Wali Songo. Gifts or offerings are made to the saint, verses from the Al-Quran are recited and pilgrims pray for favors known as ngalap berkah in Javanese., Quinn, George. *Bandit Saints of Java: How Java's Eccentric Saints Are Challenging Fundamentalist Islam in Modern Indonesia*. Burrough on the Hill, Leicester: Monsoon Books, 2019.

Reference: Other [specify]: Legend surrounding two noni trees planted outside the tomb of Sunan Giri, Susanti, Duwi, Mujiman Andianto, and Furoidhatul Husniah. "Mitos Asal Usul Buah Biji Di Lingkungan Makam Sunan Giri". *Artikel Hasil Penelitian Mahasiswa [Results of Student Research]*, December 10, 2013. <https://repository.unej.ac.id/bitstream/handle/123456789/61742/Duwi%20Susanti.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>.

Reference: Field doesn't know, Kemper, Simon. "The White Heron Called by the Muezzin: Shrines, Sufis and Warlords in Early Modern Java". In *Challenging Cosmopolitanism: Coercion, Mobility and Displacement in*, edited by Joshua Gedacht and Michael Feener. Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press, n.d.. https://www.google.co.in/books/edition/Challenging_Cosmopolitanism/C8h0DwAAQBAJ?hl=en&gbpv=1&dq=joshua+gedacht+and+michael+feener&printsec=frontcover.

Reference: Yes, Pradana, Rizal Wahyu Bagas. "Kajian Ikonografi Arsitektur Cungkup Makam Sunan Giri". *Jurusan Seni Rupa Dan Jurusan Desain Universitas Negeri Surabaya*, September 19, 2019. <https://media.neliti.com/media/publications/289424-kajian-ikonografi-arsitektur-cungkup-mak-c021dfff.pdf>.

Reference: Yes, Faidah, Mutimmatul. "Pilgrims' Spiritual Practices at the Tomb of Sunan Giri During the Covid Pandemic". *Advances in Social Science, Education and Humanities Research*, Volume 618 *International Joint Conference on Arts and Humanities 2021 (IJCAH 2021)* 618 (January 1, 2021). p.1010-14

Reference: Yes, Midaada, Arivista. "Ramalan Sunan Giri Dan Penaklukkan Mataram Atas Kesultanan Pajang Artikel Ini Telah Diterbitkan Di Halaman Sindonews.com Pada Selasa, 16 November 2021 - 10:02 WIB Oleh Avirista Midaada Dengan Judul "ramalan Sunan Giri Dan Penaklukkan Mataram Atas Kesultanan Pajang".". *Sindo News*, n.d.. <https://daerah.sidonews.com/read/600685/704/ramalan-sunan-giri-dan-penaklukkan-mataram-atas-kesultanan-pajang-1637028692>.

Reference: Yes, Susanto, Bruriy. "Peristiwa Makam Sunan Giri, Puti Napak Tilas Kakeknya". *Merdeka.com*, n.d.. <https://www.merdeka.com/peristiwa/ziarah-makam-sunan-giri-puti-napak-tilas-kakeknya.html>.

Reference: Yes, al-Ayyubi, Sudasir. "Kaum Giri Minta Bantuan Dewan Lurusan Tumpang Tindih Tupoksi Yayasan Makam Sunan Giri". Javasatu.com, n.d.. <https://jvasatu.com/culture/kaum-giri-minta-bantuan-dewan-luruskan-tumpang-tindih-tupoksi-yayasan-makam-sunan-giri/>.

Reference: Terracing, Other [specify]: The tomb complex of Sunan Giri is terraced (4 levels) whilst the tombs of Sunan Giri and his wife are located on the fourth level., Anom, I. G. N., Sri Sugiyanti, and Hadniwati Hasibuan. Hasil Pemugaran Dan Temuan Benda Cagar Budaya PJP I. Direktorat Jenderal Kebudayaan, 1996.
https://www.google.co.in/books/edition/Hasil_Pemugaran_dan_Temuan_Benda_Cagar_B/BjXkCgAAQBAJ?hl=en&gbpv=1.